

**HIGHLY SPIRITUAL IN ENSURING HUMAN VALUE
RAISING YOUNG PEOPLE IS THE HIGHEST GOAL.**

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Abstract. The education of highly meaningful and moral youth in order to ensure human value is the foundation of an independent state as well as the future. The fate and future of each society, people living in it, especially representatives of the younger generation, is of course closely connected with the upbringing of young people, which are considered the leading forces of states. In order to strengthen the creative potential of young people and representatives of the younger generation, to increase their involvement in the ongoing reforms, great work is being carried out in the country. However, the upbringing of competent, purposeful and ambitious young people with modern knowledge and skills, who take responsibility for the worthy future of the state, is one of the most urgent tasks of today.

Keywords: "a society where human dignity is a priority, a people-loving state, "For human dignity".

The education of highly meaningful and moral youth in order to ensure human value is the foundation of an independent state as well as the future. The fate and future of each society, people living in it, especially representatives of the younger generation, is of course closely connected with the upbringing of young people, which are considered the leading forces of states. In order to strengthen the creative potential of young people and representatives of the younger generation, to increase their involvement in the ongoing reforms, great work is being carried out in the country. However, the upbringing of competent, purposeful and ambitious young people with modern knowledge and skills, who take responsibility for the worthy future of the state, is one of the most urgent tasks of today. In our national and religious values, much and special attention should be paid to the delicate aspects of raising children, especially to making him a hardworking, honest, loving, strong-willed and courageous person.

Nowadays, it is worth saying with pride that our youth, with their intellectual potential, achieve great success at international Olympiads, sports competitions, and, moreover, on all fronts, defend the flag of independent Uzbekistan and the

honor of the motherland, delight everyone's language. But it is no secret that, along with our achievements and victories, there have also been cases of abuse of harmful habits among some young people. This cannot be denied. In order to prevent such negative situations, officials of all state and non-state institutions are required to approach the issues of creating a healthy environment in family, schools, educational institutions, the formation of highly spiritual youth education in ensuring human value. In order for today's youth to be free not only financially, but above all spiritually, to be able to distinguish a friend from an enemy, a good from a bad one, to be able to embody universal, national values along with a national idea, to form them, it is necessary to exalt the intelligence, taffakuri, especially spirituality of young people. In the new Uzbekistan, at a new stage of development, which is rapidly passing today, the education of a physically healthy and spiritually harmonious young generation is one of the priority areas of the country's policy. At present, it is no secret to anyone that the manifestation of the struggle for the soul and consciousness of a person, especially representatives of the younger generation, is becoming more intense than ever, and this is clearly noticeable. Due to the revival of our national heritage and values, the growing understanding of the national identity, significant positive changes are taking place in the minds, thinking of young people. Changes in spiritual and educational processes permeated the hearts and minds of young people, in which faith in their own strength, in their own possibility was carved. Young people growing up today will become the backbone of an independent homeland tomorrow. In this regard, it should be borne in mind that the higher goal is to educate young people with high spirituality in ensuring human value. It is known that the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan should put forward 5 important initiatives on the establishment of work in the social, spiritual and educational spheres on the basis of a new system, increasing attention to young people and raising their spirituality at a high level, issues of broad involvement of the younger generation in culture, sa'nat, physical education and sports, Most of the country's population is considered to be representatives of the younger generation under the age of 30. In order for them to be highly spiritual, it is necessary for young people to receive education, to master a profession. For this purpose, modern conditions and opportunities have been created for young people, and the organization of meaningful spending of their free time is an urgent issue. And in ensuring human value, the higher the spirituality of young people, the stronger their immunity to various diseases. It is known that three

years ago the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, on the initiative of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan was established, and the date of June 30 was declared "Youth Day" in the country. In addition, in the practice of Uzbekistan, a completely new system was created, namely, the Institute for the study of special-youth problems and training of promising personnel, which is engaged in the study of various pressing problems of young people. Over the past period, the legal basis of the work carried out has also been strengthened. In particular, at the initiative of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, more than 40 laws and legislative acts related to the policy of the younger generation were adopted in order to increase attention to young people, to raise their morale. Why the president of the country places a special emphasis on the issue of youth. The head of state stands at the pulpit of influential international organizations and calls on the world community to prevent the younger generation from joining various destructive ideas and alien groups. The main attention should be paid to enlightenment, raising the spiritual and moral education of young people to the highest. In our national and religious values, it is necessary to focus on the subtle aspects of raising children, especially in ensuring human value, making it have a high level of spirituality. But among the representatives of the younger generation there are also weak-willed children who tend to live a light-hearted life, have a weak faith. Young people in this category are not interested in the strange way of life, we cannot say that various show programs, nights in a foreign spirit do not penetrate their imagination and do not change their imagination. It is no secret to anyone that at present there has been an increase in means such as computers, internet clubs, television, films that are shallow in content and promote various harmful habits, tools that negatively affect the upbringing of young people. It is necessary to look at the events taking place around, not with calmness and apathy, but with sympathy. As the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan noted: "it should be clear to all of us that if carelessness and indifference reign somewhere, the most pressing issues are thrown into the self-government, then spirituality will become the most helpless and vulnerable point. And vice versa-where sympathy and vivacity, high intelligence and thinking prevail, then spirituality becomes a powerful force." The greatest wealth and invaluable treasure of Uzbekistan is youth. Raising young people with high spirituality in ensuring human value is the highest goal, representatives of the younger generation are the foundation of the future of the state. Today, there is a great meaning in the country, when all the strength and opportunities are being launched for the perfect acquisition of

young people by modern science and high technologies, in particular, the president and the creation of schools. It is necessary to highly educate the morale of young people who are currently studying in educational buildings equipped with modern requirements and with all conditions. The head of State expressed one opinion: “when the body of the life of society is the economy, its soul, its soul is spirituality. Because without spiritual foundations, without spiritual foundations, without spiritual values, without spiritual-national authority, no state will achieve its high goals.” In order to educate young people with a high level of spirituality in ensuring human value, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 14.01.2018 “on measures to educate young people spiritually and morally and physically well-being, to qualitatively raise the system of education and education to a new level” PP-3907, measures were taken to form a harmonious generation in

And the state policy on the spiritual and moral tasks of young people implemented in the country today shows the importance of our national and religious values, which have long been formed by our ancestors. However, tomorrow's prosperous life is determined by building society according to the principles of perfect morality, raising a harmonious child in the family, having his physically contactless, spiritually refreshed, spiritually high, mentally and morally beautiful qualities. The Blessed khadisi Sharif, quoted in the book “The masterpieces of decency” by our great-great-grandfather Imam Bukhari, says that “no father can give his child a greater inheritance than a Hulk-he is polite.” After all, the upbringing of high spiritual and moral youth is the foundation of a bright future. In the country, the attitude towards the huge heritage of allomas, who contributed to the development of the history, culture, material and spiritual wealth of our people, world food, has changed dramatically. They increased attention to the restoration of their heritage, historical figures, great scholars, cities, historical monuments. Drawing such conclusions from the above, it should be said that, paying special attention to youth education, one should jointly fight against vices that are not inherent in society, feeling all responsibility, not forgetting that raising young people with high spirituality is the highest goal in ensuring human value. It is important to remember that youth is the next of any society. The struggle between destructive and enlightened ideas for their consciousness will continue. After all, young harmonious generation and patriotic youth with high spirituality and high morality in ensuring human dignity are true followers of today and tomorrow.

used literature:

1. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 14.08.2018 PQ-3907 "on measures to raise the system of moral and moral and physical education of young people, to a qualitatively new level." Lex. An-line away.
2. I.Nishanov - "raising high spiritual youth is our supreme goal." Fergana. Justice. uz. - article in the issue of 30.12.015 P. 2.
3. U.Gafurov - "the foundation of the future of high spiritual youth." Article of the committee on religious affairs in fasting P .1.
4. O.Shukurov - "spiritual and moral youth-the foundation of a bright future." Article in the fast "Justice" dated 06.07.2020 No. 2651 P .1.
5. O.Atakhanova. Article No. 10606" foundation of our future and future of the youth of New Uzbekistan "in the fast" people's word " pp. 2 .
6. R.Gaipnazarov."Spiritual youth is the backbone of the motherland." Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan web.website. Article No. 921 dated 01/25/2021 Page 1

